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Effect Of Economic Crisis On Academic Achievement Of University Students In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The recent economic crisis in Nigeria has had a significant impact on the academic achievement of university students. The high unemployment rates and the inflation have caused financial strain on families making it difficult for students to afford tuition fees as well as educational resources, which significantly contributed to the decline of the students' academic performance for effective human development. This paper focused on the effect of economic crisis of university students on their academic achievement. The main objective of this study is to find out the extent to which the economic crisis affects Academic Achievement of University Students. Descriptive survey research design was used and quantitative approach was used because the data analysis technique is statistical in purpose to get clear answers to the research questions. The populations of this study will be students from faculties in the university. This consisted of 5 Faculties. Population of 600 undergraduate students will be considered. 234 participants out of 600 were considered in the selected faculties from the five (5) faculties in the university. The findings of the research revealed that has also had a negative impact on the mental health of students. The financial stress and uncertainty about their future prospect have led to increased level s of anxiety, depression, and other mental health and socio-economic issues which affect students' academic achievements in the institution among which are inadequate money to pay for health facilities usage in the institution, rapid-annual school tuition fee increment, lack of frequent funding from the government for operating expenses. The study recommended that, the school management as the directors of academic activities in the institutions should always ensure proper coordination of regulation of cost of the educational services around the campus so that students' can purchase at their level of financial ability. Furthermore, the government and other stakeholders should create more sponsors and scholarship for students to have ease in their academic struggled.

Keywords: Economic Crisis, University, Students, Academic Achievement

INTRODUCTION

Economic crisis is a universal phenomenon in almost all countries of the world and has attracted the attention of researchers (Hernández & Kriesi, 2016). Economic crisis is a significant decline in daily activities across the economy, lasting longer than a few months. It is visible in decline in industrial production, employment, real income and wholesale-retail trade (Tijani & Abdullahi, 2021). However, there is economic crisis in Nigeria which affects all sectors including educational sector (Akinbobola & Bada, 2018). Stakeholders in the education sector have continued to express serious concern about the poor academic achievement of students at all levels of educational system especially in the recent times. The present occurrence of economic crisis has brought untold difficulties on the academic achievement of students in different level of education. According to Adeyemi, Omoyiola and Oladejo (2021) education, particularly higher education in Nigeria is regarded by the government as one of the bedrock of attaining successful life in the society and the entire citizens regard it as capable of achieving rapid development and national integration and bringing about desirable change in all spheres of human endeavours through the skills and knowledge acquired. This may explain why the various levels of government strive to achieve the goal of providing qualitative education to the ever rising population of school aged children in realization of the roles of education in accelerating economic performances in internal and external examinations which is the yardstick for measuring the success or otherwise of the education sector.

According to Smith, Ali, Wilkerson, Dawson, Sobowale, Reynolds and Eyre (2021) the current economic crisis confronting many governments is creating severe conflicts in educational sector of many nations including Nigeria. On one hand, they had to reduce their budget deficits to avoid excess indebtedness; on the other hand, they had to promote education in order to alleviate unemployment as a short run crisis measure and to avoid the deterioration of human capital in the long run. In Nigeria, high percentage of national is on the public funding, which greatly affect the education sector. These had negative effects on teachers, students and families.

Statement Of The Problem

The base of University education are closely tied to the government funding programs in the Universities, lack of funding of programs has directly affect to public poverty level, especially students. In other hand the performance of a country's economy can sincerely make the difference between a bright future or a lost generation. University level of education is the worst hit by the down turn in our economy in the sense that the number of demands in the universities increases such as salary, maintenance, and students' basic needs in the university. The lofty objectives of university education might not be achieved due to myriads of economic problems affecting it. This development has led to serious comparison between the academic achievements of students before the period of economic meltdown and the presents state of economic crisis, hence the need to research on the composite and independent contributions of economic crisis on students' academic achievement, particularly in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto. This situation however, formed the basis for the current study. Hence, the researchers intended to investigate or find out the effect of economic crisis among University students on their academic achievement of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The main objectives of this study is to find out the meaning of Economic crisis on academic achievement of student in University, Nigeria, and the extent to which the economic crisis affect Academic Achievement of University Students.

Research Questions

This research work attempt to answer the following questions:

1. What is Economic Crises on students' academic achievement?
2. How does Economic Crisis Affect Academic Achievement of University Students?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The responsibility of training a child always lies in the hand of the parents. Parental educational background, profession and occupation affect their financial status. Family income is one major factor that affects their children's educational level, competitive ability and performance. A sound mind

lives in a sound body is a relevant adage to this phenomenon. Some researchers uphold that parents' socio-economic status (or social classes) affects children's rate of retentive memory and deviation and academic achievement (Reindolf, Oliver & Emmanuel, 2016).

Hijazi in Reindolf, Oliver and Emmanuel (2016) explained that the relationship between students' academic achievement and student family income is positive because money can buy you all the comforts that you need to concentrate on their studies but interestingly the result also shows that students belonging to more prosperous families do not give proper attention to studies, thus affluence cannot make a student necessarily serious about his/her studies.

The poor financial conditions affecting most native communities, damage self-esteem and can result in depression, drug and violence, all of which contribute to the high suicide rate. Corby and Benjamin (2018) asserted that differences in performance exist among the various financial aid participants and non-financial aid participants, these differences cannot be attributed to the financial aid group alone. Variables, both demographic and college specific are interacting with each other to form significant combination.

Kanwai (2016) explained that financial crisis on the maintenance of facilities in the institution such as hostel accommodation; lecture rooms, textbooks, etc are not in proper condition. The hostel accommodation is not conducive for the students; in the lecture rooms, you find some students hanging on windows and some sitting on bare floor during lectures. If the student is not psychologically balanced, this may lead to low academic performance. Also in the libraries, there are not enough textbooks for the students to use, even if there are, they are not recent publications. Because of constant power failure, the library is often hot and most of the reference books are not there. The reading chairs are also unable to meet up with the geometric increase in the school enrolment.

According to Walker and Mkwanzani (2015) higher education is linked to economic mobility, public tertiary institutions demand for access to funding for education which far exceeds supply. In terms of access, part of the problem is that although the number of higher education students has drastically increased in the last 10 years, peaking in 2011, all universities are now subjected to strict enrolment plans. Thus enrolment numbers are capped. So, some students will have their applications declined even though they may qualify for admission. But, there are additional hurdles for those who are admitted, in that they will not necessarily be in a position to pay their fees. While some qualify for standalone independent bursaries from industry or other donors, and others qualify for National Student Financial Aid Scheme (NSFAS) funding, there are those who do not.

Oyelana (2017) in his article explained that South African students without bursaries have to seek out bank loans or rely on part-time work, savings and parental or family contributions to pay for their studies. But not all qualify for bank loans, or can find part-time work and some do not have family who can support them. Importantly, tertiary education is very expensive for most South Africans as there are many additional non-tuition costs such as living expenses, textbooks and other academic related costs (such as internet access), transport costs and lifestyle costs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a descriptive survey research design, According to Creswell and Creswell (2017) the design enables researcher to ascertain the extent to which a variation in one variable is associated with variation in another. The populations of this study were students from faculties in the University of Usmanu Danfodiyo consisted of 5 Faculties. Populations of 600 undergraduate students were considered from which the data necessary for the completion of this research was obtain. Purposive sampling was employed to select the respondents from the five (5) faculties in the University, 234 participants out of 600 were purposively selected in the faculties from the 5 faculties in the university. Self-constructed questionnaire titled Students' School Expenses Rating Scale (SSAERS) based on five (5) points rating agreement was used to collect the data needed in this study. Specifically, descriptive statistics (Aggregate Percentage) was used to analyze the data obtained from the Research Questions.

RESULT

Answers to Research Questions:

This sections present answers to research questions as follows:

Research Question 1: What is Economic Crises on students' academic achievement?

Answer 1: Socio-Economic Crisis that Affect Students' Academic Achievement in the University

Table 1: Socio-Economic Crisis that Affect Students' Academic Achievement of Students in the University

S/No.	Item Statement	Agreed	%	Disagree	%
1.	Inadequate money to pay for facilities usage in school affect academic achievement	64	55.1	56	44.9
2.	Reduction of income can affect academic achievement	58	49.3	62	50.7
3.	Cost of study material in environment may affects students' academic achievement	65	57.4	55	42.6
4.	Poor supplies of health facilities for students lead to poor academic achievement	68	59.9	52	40.1
5.	Inadequate token for students' assistance affect their academic achievement	64	55.1	56	44.9
Percentage aggregate			55.36%		44.64%

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 1 showed that percentage aggregate of 55.36% of the respondents totally agreed that among the socio-economic crisis that affect students' academic achievement are: Inadequate money to pay for facilities usage in school, Reduction of income; Cost of study material in environment, Poor supplies of health facilities for students and Inadequate token for students' assistance, while 44.64% aggregate percentage disagree with the statements. This indicated that majority of the students were all agreed that socio-economic crisis mentioned in the table affect academic achievement of students in the university.

Answer 2: Financial Crises that affect Students' Academic Achievement in University

Table 2: Financial Crises that affect Students' Academic Achievement in University

S/No.	Item Statement	Agreed	%	Disagree	%
1.	Rapid/annual school tuition fee increment affect academic achievement	64	55.1	56	44.9
2.	Reduction of income expected from the parent by the students affect academic achievement	58	49.3	62	50.7
3.	Hike in the cost of education supplies affect academic achievement	65	57.4	55	42.6
4.	Reduction of benefits the tutors/lectures affect academic achievement	68	59.9	52	40.1
5.	Less intervention to help education state and federal affect academic achievement	64	55.1	56	44.9
Percentage aggregate			55.36%		44.64%

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 2 showed that percentage aggregate of 55.36% of the respondents totally agreed that among the financial crises that affect the academic achievement of students in the university are; Rapid/annual school tuition fee increment, Reduction of income expected from the parent by the students, Hike in the cost of education supplies, Reduction of benefits the tutors/lectures and Less intervention to help education from the government of state and federal. While percentage aggregate 44.64% were

disagreed with the statement. This indicated that majority of the students were all agreed that financial crisis mentioned in the table affected the academic achievement of students in the university.

Research Question 2: *How does Economic Crisis Affect Academic Achievement of University Students?*

Answer: Financial Crises that affect Students' Academic Achievement in University

Table 3: Financial Crises that affect Students' Academic Achievement in University

S/No.	Item Statement	Agreed	%	Disagree	%
1.	Rapid/annual school tuition fee increment affect academic achievement	64	55.1	56	44.9
2.	Reduction of income expected from the parent by the students affect academic achievement	58	49.3	62	50.7
3.	Hike in the cost of education supplies affect academic achievement	65	57.4	55	42.6
4.	Reduction of benefits the tutors/lectures affect academic achievement	68	59.9	52	40.1
5.	Less intervention to help education state and federal affect academic achievement	64	55.1	56	44.9
Percentage aggregate			55.36%		44.64%

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 3 showed that percentage aggregate of 55.36% of the respondents totally agreed that among the financial crises that affect the academic achievement of students in the university are; Rapid/annual school tuition fee increment, Reduction of income expected from the parent by the students, Hike in the cost of education supplies, Reduction of benefits the tutors/lectures and Less intervention to help education from the government of state and federal. While percentage aggregate 44.64% were disagreed with the statement. This indicated that majority of the students were all agreed that financial crisis mentioned in the table affected the academic achievement of students in the university.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from the research question one show that among the socio-economic crisis which affected the students' academic achievement in the university include Inadequate money to pay for facilities usage in school affect academic achievement, Reduction of parents' income can affect academic achievement, Cost of study material in environment may affects students' academic achievement, Poor supplies of health facilities for students affect their academic achievement and Inadequate token for students' assistance affect their academic achievement affect students' academic achievement . This is in line with Adeyanju and Adu (2013) who stated that the results in shortage of material and human resources experienced in the system. Inadequate qualified educators, high turnover rate of teachers, shortage of classroom, and poor remuneration of tutors and a host of other problems abound in the education sector.

The findings from the research question two also indicated that there are other financial crisis which also affected the students' academic achievement which include, Rapid/annual school tuition fee increment affect academic achievement, Reduction of income expected from the parent by the students affect academic achievement, Hike in the cost of education supplies affect academic achievement, Reduction of benefits the tutors/lectures affect students' academic achievement and Less intervention to help education affect students' academic achievement. This in line with Martins and Emmanuel (2009) declared that the immediate effect of economic meltdown on organizations and the inability to maintain the current productive capacity leading to inadequate fund. It raises the possible implication of government's control measures such as cutting down expenditure which may likely affect educational expenditure.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The research found out that inadequate money to pay for facilities usage in school affect academic achievement, Reduction of parents' income can affect academic achievement, Cost of study material in environment may affects students' academic achievement, Poor supplies of health facilities for students affect their academic achievement and Inadequate token for students' assistance affect their academic achievement affect students' academic achievement. there are other financial crisis which also affected the students' academic achievement which include, Rapid/annual school tuition fee increment affect academic achievement, Reduction of income expected from the parent by the students affect academic achievement, Hike in the cost of education supplies affect academic achievement, Reduction of benefits the tutors/lectures affect students' academic achievement and Less intervention to help education affect students' academic achievement. Finally the study also finds out that there are economic differences which also affected the students' academic achievement in the university these includes; Unavailability of learning technologies in the campus affect students' academic achievement, Inadequate to access of internet service network in the school affect students' academic achievement, Lack of frequent funding from the government for operating expenses in the school affect students' academic achievement, Lack of social services in the school for students affect students' academic achievement and Lack of research funding and training grants for students affect students' academic achievement.

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are provided.

1. The institutions should always ensure that their responsibility as the directors of the activities in the school that they always coordination the cost of the commodities around the campus so that students' can purchase at their level of financial ability.
2. They should report any difficult situation concerning the economy of the school to the public for immediate intervention and preparation by the parents before the commencement of any payment of expenses in the institutions.
3. They should also involve the community through meetings for any decision concerning the economic situation of the in the school before taking any actions.
4. Training of students on skills and retraining of staff should be organized by the involvement of state ministry of higher education for their financial support and assistance since there are students and staffs who are indigene to the state so that acquire more skills for effective academic achievement.
5. There is also need for another research to be carried out to investigate the other effect of effect of economic crisis on students' academic performance in other institution using different variables.

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